

FINDING THE NUMBER OF PYTHAGOREAN PAIRS OF A NATURAL NUMBER THAT ARE NOT COMMON BASES

Ibragimov Husniddin Hikmatovich

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17548901>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th October 2025

Accepted: 04th November 2025

Online: 05th November 2025

KEYWORDS

Pythagorean theorem, Pythagorean pairs, Euler triples, Euler brick, diagonal, right triangle, equilateral triangle.

ABSTRACT

The following explains that if $(a,b;c)$ is a Pythagorean pair, then the number a is a Pythagorean pair of the number b , and the Pythagorean triples \dots , then the Pythagorean pairs for the number a are given. It is also stated that if the number a is a Pythagorean pair of the number b , then the number b is also a Pythagorean pair of the number a . Pythagorean numbers, determining the number of Pythagorean pairs of a Pythagorean number are explained.

NATURAL SONNING O'ZARO TUB BO'LMAGAN PIFAGOR JUFTLARI SONINI TOPISH

Ibragimov Husniddin Hikmatovich

Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti, Surxondaryo, Denov

Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy, Surkhondaryo, Denov

e-mail: husniddinhikmatovich@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17548901>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th October 2025

Accepted: 04th November 2025

Online: 05th November 2025

KEYWORDS

Pifagor soni, Pifagor juftlari, Eyler uchligii, Eyler g'ishti, diagonal, to'g'ri burchakli uchburchak, teng yonli uchburchak.

ABSTRACT

Quyida $(a,b;c)$ Pifagor juftligi bo'lsa, u holda a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lishi haqida, Pifagor uchliklari $(a, b_1; c_1), (a, b_2; c_2), \dots, (a, b_n; c_n)$ berilganda u holda a soni uchun b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n Pifagor juftlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lsa, u holda b soni ham a sonining Pifagor jufti ekanligi keltirilgan. Pifagor sonlari, biror Pifagor soning Pifagor juftlari sonini aniqlash yoritilgan.

Ma'lumki, istalgan $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$, $n > m$ sonlari yordamida hosil qilingan

$$a = n^2 - m^2, \quad b = 2nm, \quad c = n^2 + m^2 \quad (1)$$

$(a, b; c)$ uchlik Pifagor uchligini bo'ladi. (1) formula yordamida istalgan Pifagor uchligini hosil qilish mumkin [1]- [5].

Endi bir Pifagor uchligi berilgan bo'lsa, uning yordamida yangi Pifagor uchligini hosil qilish usulini bayon qilamiz.

2.5-ta'rif. Agar $(a, b; c)$ Pifagor juftligi bo'lsa, u holda a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti deyiladi.

Bizga Pifagor uchliklari $(a, b_1; c_1), (a, b_2; c_2), \dots, (a, b_n; c_n)$ berilsin, u holda a soni uchun b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n sonlari Pifagor juftlari deb ataladi.

Ta'rifdan kelib chiqadiki, agar a soni b sonining Pifagor jufti bo'lsa, u holda b soni ham a sonining Pifagor jufti bo'ladi.

2.1-teorema. $n = 2k, \forall k \in N$ juft sonlar Pifagor juftlari (PJS) soni

$$(PJS) (2k) = \frac{NBS(k^2) - 1}{2}$$

2.2-teorema. Ixtiyoriy $n = 2k + 1, \forall k \in N$ toq sonning Pifagor juftlari soni

$$PJS(2k + 1) = \frac{NBS((2k+1)^2) - 1}{2}$$

$$(2n)^2 + \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$\forall n, p_i \in Z$ uchun bunday Pifagor juftlarining soni $((p_i - n^2$ ning turli bo'luvchilari) $\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i - p_i < x$ tengsizligini qanoatlantiruvchi butun sonlar soni. Agar biz ayniyatning ikkala qismini p_i ning kvadratiga ko'paytirsak, u holda biz barcha Pifagor sonlarini beradigan klassik formulani olamiz, ya'ni ular orasida $2n$ juft sonli barcha Pifagor juftlari bor, ya'ni

$$(2n)^2 + \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{n^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$$4n^2 + \frac{n^4}{p_i^2} - 2n^2 + p_i^2 = \frac{n^4}{p_i^2} + 2n^2 + p_i^2$$

tenglik bajariladi va $2n$ juft soni Pifagor juftlarining soni $\frac{n^2}{p_i} - p_i$ sonining butun son yekanligiga bog'liqligidan, u holda $n = 2k, \forall k \in N$ juft soni Pifagor juftlari

$$(PJS) (2k) = \frac{NBS(k^2) - 1}{2}$$

2.1-misol. 72 sonining Pifagor juftlarini topamiz.

Yechish. 1-usul. $k=36$ bo'lgani uchun

$$(2.36)^2 + \left(\frac{36^2}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{36^2}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$$(2.36)^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i} - p_i\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i} + p_i\right)^2$$

$\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{p_i}$ kasr butun songa teng bo'lgan shunday $p_i < 36$ ni topamiz.

$$p_1 = 1, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{1} - 1\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{1} + 1\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 1295^2 = 1297^2$$

$$p_2 = 2, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{2} - 2\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{2} + 2\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 646^2 = 650^2$$

$$p_3 = 3, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{3} - 3\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{3} + 3\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 429^2 = 435^2$$

$$p_4 = 4, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{4} - 4\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{4} + 4\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 320^2 = 328^2$$

$$p_5 = 6, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{6} - 6\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{6} + 6\right)^2 \quad 72^2 + 210^2 = 222^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_6 = 8, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{8} - 8\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{8} + 8\right)^2 & 72^2 + 154^2 &= 170^2 \\
 p_7 = 9, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{9} - 9\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{9} + 9\right)^2 & 72^2 + 135^2 &= 153^2 \\
 p_8 = 12, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{12} - 12\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{12} + 12\right)^2 & 72^2 + 96^2 &= 120^2 \\
 p_9 = 16, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{16} - 16\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{16} + 16\right)^2 & 72^2 + 65^2 &= 97^2 \\
 p_{10} = 18, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} - 18\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} + 18\right)^2 & 72^2 + 54^2 &= 90^2 \\
 p_{11} = 24, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} - 18\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{18} + 18\right)^2 & 72^2 + 54^2 &= 90^2 \\
 p_{12} = 27, \quad 72^2 + \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{27} - 27\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 3^4}{27} + 27\right)^2 & 72^2 + 21^2 &= 75^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Bundan kelib chiqadiki, biz 72 sonining barcha natural bo'luvchilari sonini topdik.
Demak, (PJS) (72)=12.

2-usul. 1-teorema asosida buni ham topish mumkin

$$PJS(72) = \frac{NBS(36^2) - 1}{2} = 12$$

2-misol. 15 sonining Pifagor juftlarini topamiz.

Yechish. 1-usul.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_1 = 1, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 - 1}{2}\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 + 1}{2}\right)^2 & 15^2 + 112^2 &= 113^2 \\
 p_2 = 3, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 - 3}{2}\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 + 3}{2}\right)^2 & 15^2 + 35^2 &= 38^2 \\
 p_3 = 5, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 - 5}{2}\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 + 5}{2}\right)^2 & 15^2 + 20^2 &= 25^2 \\
 p_3 = 9, \quad 15^2 + \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 - 9}{2}\right)^2 &= \left(\frac{3^2 \cdot 5^2 + 9}{2}\right)^2 & 15^2 + 8^2 &= 17^2
 \end{aligned}$$

2-usul. 2-teoremadan foydalanib, topamiz

$$PJS(15) = \frac{NBS((2k + 1)^2) - 1}{2} = 4$$

References:

1. A. A'zamov. *Eyler g'ishtlari*. Fizika, matematika va informatika. 2012. №1, 52-56.
2. Abdullayev J.I., Ibragimov H. H. *Pifagor taxtasi yordamida Pifagor g'ishtlarini qurish*. Ilmiy axborotnoma. Samarqand, 1-son (119), 2020. 15-21.
3. Abdullayev J.I., Ibragimov H. H. *Pifagor va Eyler g'ishtlari*. Buxoro davlat universiteti Ilmiy axboroti. Buxoro, 2022/6(94). 10-15.
4. Abdullayev J.I., Ibragimov H. H. *Pifagor va Eyler g'ishtlari uchun parametrik tenglamalar*. Ilmiy axborotnoma. Samarqand, №3/(139) 2023.29-34.
5. H.H.Ibragimov. *Pifagor sonlari va Eyler g'ishti*. Tadbirkorlik va pedagogika. Ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal. 2023-yil, 1-son, 198-207 betlar.
6. By Samuel Bonaya Buya end Whiteeagle Joshua Daddah. *A method of Finding Perfect Euler Bricks*. 07.01.2017. 1-15.
7. Oliver Knill. *Treasure Hunting Perfect Euler bricks*. 24.02.2009. 1-5.